

DIPOLE MOMENT AND STRUCTURE OF HEXACHLOROCYCLOHEXANES

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Commercial hexachlorocyclohexane was separated into four isomers: α , β , γ and δ melting at 156° , 309° , 112.6° and 138° respectively, by fractional crystallisation from methyl alcohol. The dielectric constants and densities of the isomers were measured in different solvents and the dipole moments of the isomers were calculated by applying the new equation. The results are used to ascribe the structures to the isomers. β and δ isomers have symmetrical structures. The moment $2.55D$ of γ -isomer, which has five equatorial and one polar chlorine atoms, is explained as the vector of two C—Cl bonds at tetrahedral angle, the remaining bonds cancelling out. The moment $1.7D$ for the α -isomer is explained on the basis of the flexible boat form which has the highest energy content and which forms 70% of the product. The heat of vaporisation of the β -isomer is lowest (11.87 K cal.) and of others, about 13.6 K cal. The infra-red spectra support the structures assigned to the various isomers. The study of alkaline dehydrochlorination of the isomers indicates the order of hydrolysis as $\alpha > \delta > \gamma > \epsilon$, the β -isomer being inert. The correlation between the insecticidal property and the dipole moment of the isomers reveals the fact that in this series the dipole moment varies linearly with the logarithm of the mortality coefficient K and that the γ -isomer, which possesses outstanding insecticidal properties, has high dipole moment.

The determination of the molecular structure of different isomers of hexachlorocyclohexanes would be of great interest, as one of the isomers is well known to be a powerful insecticide.

Hexachlorocyclohexane was first prepared by Faraday (1825) by passing a current of chlorine in benzene in the presence of sunlight. Matthews (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 59, 166) showed that it contained two isomers. Van der Linden (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 231) proved the existence of four isomers. Thomas (cf. Slade, *Chem. Ind.*, 1945, 64, 314) showed that the γ -isomer was the most powerful insecticide. Recently Kauer *et al.* (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1947, 39, 1335) have isolated the fifth isomer ϵ (m. p. 219°) and shown that it is non-toxic to insects.

Williams and Fogelberg (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 2098) have reported the dipole moments for the α - and β -isomers. Hassel (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, B15, 373) showed that the moment of β -isomer was zero. Slade (*loc. cit.*) has stated that of the 16 possible isomers of hexachlorocyclohexanes only four are strainless (chair) forms. According to Daasch (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1947, 19, 779), in addition to the four chair forms of hexachlorocyclohexanes, there is one boat (flexible) form which could also occur as a mirror-image. Since the ϵ -isomer concentration is the lowest (3%) in the mixture, the boat form corresponds to the configuration of ϵ -isomer according to Daasch (*loc. cit.*).

The present authors (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1949, Part III, p. 26; *Science & Culture*, 1949, 11, 482; *Chem. Abstract*, 1949, 43, 6877) have isolated the

four isomers, α , β , δ and γ , from the commercial mixture of hexachlorocyclohexane and determined the dipole moments with a view to substantiating the structures assigned to them and also to correlating the insecticidal property with the data on dipole moment.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Pure Isomers from the Crude Materials

The four isomers, α , β , γ and δ , were isolated from the crude material by the method worked out by Smart (cf. Slade, *loc. cit.*). The crude hexachlorocyclohexane was treated with a small amount of methyl alcohol in which the α - and β -forms are relatively insoluble. Separation of the solid (I) leaves a solution containing the γ and δ and other lower chlorinated substances and very little α and β . The solution was evaporated to half its volume, when a small crop of practically pure γ (II, m.p. 110°) was obtained. Next crop obtained on further evaporation, contained γ , little α and β (III). Pure γ was prepared from (II) by recrystallising twice from chloroform and four times from carbon tetrachloride. Pure δ was obtained with difficulty from (III) by pouring the methanol solution in petroleum ether and finally recrystallising from chloroform. α and β were isolated from (I) by treatment with chloroform in which β was practically insoluble (0.3%) and pure α was obtained by recrystallising from benzene. The residue, containing mostly β , was washed with chloroform to remove traces of impurities of other isomers and was finally recrystallised from acetone. The melting points of pure isomers are: α , 158°; β , 309°; γ , 112.5°; δ , 138° in agreement with the values reported by others.

The dielectric constant and density of these isomers were measured in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and dioxane; the dielectric constant of pure molten γ -isomer was also measured between 113° and 150°. Dipole moment was calculated by applying the new equation (Jatkar *et al.*, *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1946, 28A, Part II),

$$P = (\epsilon - 1) M/d; P_E = (n^2 - 1) M/d;$$

$$P - P_E = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{kT} \text{ for pure liquid and}$$

$$p_{12} = \frac{\epsilon_{12} - 1}{d_{12}} = p_1 w_1 + p_2 w_2 \text{ and } P_2 = p_2 M_2 \text{ for solutions,}$$

where w_2 is the weight fraction of the solute. The value of the electronic polarisation (P_E) calculated from the refractive index and density given by Hassel (*Tids. kjemi Berg.*, 1930, 81, 126) is 270. The results are given in the following tables.

TABLE I

Dielectric constant and dipole moment of hexachlorocyclohexane.

t°	Solvent.	w_2	ϵ	d	P_2	$\mu \times 10^{18}$
α-Hexachlorocyclohexane.						
25°	C_6H_6	(a) 0.0000	2.276	0.8735	(114.1)	...
		0.0012	2.285	0.8755	835.8	1.74
		0.0031	2.296	0.8786	689.7	1.76
		0.0061	2.310	0.8830	651.6	1.77
		0.0091	2.310	0.8877	652.2	1.77
25°	..	0.0692	2.3841	0.9016	743.0	1.70
		0.0729	2.4035	0.9070	770.9	1.71
40°	..	0.0682	2.3063	0.8853	740.0	1.87
		0.0729	2.3379	0.8828	752.1	1.70
25°	$C_4H_8O_2$	0.1608	2.5365	1.0973	747.2	1.70
40°	..	0.1608	2.4798	1.0828	690.0	(1.60)
β-Hexachlorocyclohexane.						
23°	$C_4H_8O_2$	0.0220	2.2456	1.0380	191.0	0.00
		0.0396	2.1654	1.0776	...	0.00
γ-Hexachlorocyclohexane (Gammexane).						
25°	C_6H_6	0.0780	2.5836	0.9092	1471.9	2.53
		0.1218	2.7546	0.9287	1457.7	2.53
40°	..	0.0780	2.5485	0.8925	1447.0	2.57
		0.1218	2.7023	0.9199	1365.0	2.53
25°	CCl_4	0.0288	2.4037	1.5910	1340.0	2.50
		0.0819	2.4310	1.5906	1363.0	2.52
40°	..	0.0288	2.3695	1.5634	1260.0	2.50
		0.0819	2.4037	1.5631	1360.0	2.53
25°	$C_4H_8O_2$	0.0564	2.4929	1.0528	1587.0	(2.60)
		0.0799	2.5446	1.0627	1351.0	2.53
40°	..	0.0564	2.4478	1.0384	1478.0	(2.61)
		0.0799	2.5058	1.0464	1300.0	2.53
δ-Hexachlorocyclohexane.						
25°	C_6H_6	0.0537	2.3406	0.8981	90.5	0.0
40°	..	0.0537	2.2375	0.8900	124.5	0.0
t°	ϵ		d	P	$\mu \times 10^{18}$	
γ-Hexachlorocyclohexane (Gemmexane), (pure molten liquid).						
159°	6.900		1.558	1102.8	2.55	
142°	7.283		1.574	1162.8	2.58	
129°	7.559		1.568	1201.3	2.59	
118°	7.857		1.604	1249.3	2.60	
23°	Solid } 2.558 }					

(a) f_2 , mole fractions (data from Williams and Fogelberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 2098, 1936). The rest by the present authors.

DISCUSSION

Sachse (*Ber.*, 1896, 13, 1363) in his theory of strainless ring postulated that a ring such as *cyclohexane*, would be able to take two configurations, now commonly designated as C or boat form and Z or chair (planar) form. Hassel (*loc. cit.*) investigated the properties of monochloro*cyclohexane* and came to the conclusion that in the Z (chair) form, chlorine was able to assume two positions which were interconvertible in the C form. The two types of valence bonds, parallel and perpendicular to the plane of the ring, may be termed equatorial and polar (cf. Beckett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2488). Of the two hydrogen atoms on each carbon atom, one is polar and one is equatorial.

In the planer (Z) form, there are three polar hydrogens (1', 3', 5') above and three (2', 4', 6') below the plane of the ring, while the six hydrogen atoms (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6) lie on the belt around the carbon ring.

Based upon Z (planar, rigid) form of the *cyclohexane* ring, there are 16 possible configurations for hexachloro*cyclohexanes*, but owing to the strain involved in the close approach of the chlorine atoms, only four strainless configurations are possible, out of which one can exist as the mirror-image. As the two types of bonds, polar and equatorial, are interconvertible in the C (flexible) form of the *cyclohexane* ring, there is only one strainless form of hexachloro*cyclohexane* in the C (flexible) form. Therefore, the possible number of isomers of hexachloro*cyclohexanes* is five, four in rigid Z form and one in flexible C form.

Dipole Moment and Structure of the Isomers

β-Isomer.—Dickinson and Bilike (*ibid.*, 1928, 50, 764) on X-ray study of the *β*-isomer (m. p. 309°) found that the *cyclohexane* ring in *β* has centrosymmetrical structure, with all the chlorine atoms evenly distributed. The dipole moment of *β*-isomer has been reported to be 0.7 in benzene and 2.0 in dioxane by Williams and Fogelberg (*loc. cit.*). The recalculated value of the moment from data in benzene is 0.2. However, Hassel (*loc. cit.*) has shown that the moment of *β* in benzene is zero and the present work confirms that the moment of *β*-isomer (m. p. 309°) in dioxane also is zero. The structure of the *β*-isomer is (i) in which there are 6 equatorial chlorine atoms and 6 polar hydrogen atoms above and below the plane of the ring.

γ-Isomer.—The observed moment for *γ*-isomer (m. p. 1125°) is 2.55, which can be explained on the basis of the structure (ii) which has five

equatorial and one polar chlorine atoms. Two pairs of equatorial chlorine atoms oppose each other, out of the remaining, one equatorial chlorine and one polar chlorine make a tetrahedral angle; taking the bond moment C—Cl, 1.69 and C—H, 0.4, the resultant vector moment for γ is 2.5 which is in very good agreement with the observed value.

δ -Isomer.—The moment of δ -isomer (m. p. 138°) is zero which could be explained by a configuration with two polar chlorine atoms ($1', 4'$) and four equatorial (2, 3, 5 and 6) chlorine atoms, which form three opposite pairs, making the isomer a symmetrical molecule.

α -Isomer.—The observed moment of α -isomer (m.p. 158°) 1.7D, is in agreement with the recalculated data of Williams and Fogelberg (*loc. cit.*). According to Slade (*loc. cit.*) the configuration (IV) with two polar ($1', 2'$) and four equatorial (3, 4, 5, 6) chlorine atoms represents the α -isomer. The moment calculated for this configuration is 3.6D. Hence, this assumption is incorrect. The moment calculated for the flexible structure, (boat or C form) with two chlorine atoms on the stern and the bow of the boat and the remaining four chlorine atoms equatorial, is 1.70D, in agreement with the observed value for the isomer α , melting at 158° . It is interesting to note that α -isomer forms 70% of the total product due to its strainless structure, which has accordingly a low toxicity. This finding is of interest in view of the possibility of converting the flexible form into some of the more useful rigid form e. g., γ -isomer by heating with aluminium trichloride.

ϵ -Isomer.—According to Daasch (*loc. cit.*) β - and ϵ -isomers are spectrally similar in shorter wave-length regions (2 to $10\text{ m}\mu$), the most striking feature of these two spectra being the simplicity when compared with those of the

other isomers. Naturally it follows that the *cyclohexane* ring in the β - and ϵ -isomers should have the same forms, either rigid Z (chair) or flexible C (boat) forms and as the X-ray and electron diffraction data (Hassel, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1942, II, 878) have established the existence of Z form of the *cyclohexane* ring in the β -isomer (m. p. 309°) it is quite evident that the ϵ -isomer (m. p. 219°) should also have Z form and not the flexible form as assumed by Daasch. It will be interesting to investigate the dipole moment of this isomer, which should be $3.6D$.

The structures of the isomers are therefore, as shown above.

Subsequent work has been published on the structures of the various isomers of hexachloro*cyclohexane*. By means of the Fourier-projections of the gammexane cell Bijvoet (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1948, 67, 777) has assigned 1', 2', 3', 4, 5, 6, *i. e.*,

configuration to γ -isomer. Since due to steric hinderance no two polar Cl atoms can be present in *meta* position, this author has predicted deformation of valency angles between the two C—Cl bonds. The dipole moment of the isomer with this configuration should be very high (about $3.55D$), whereas the observed moment is $2.5D$. Bastiansen and Hassel (*Research*, 1949, 2, 248) have ascribed structure (iii) for ϵ -isomer and have reported the dipole moment of this isomer to be zero. However, no data are available. Present authors have already shown that the δ -isomer with configuration (iii) has zero dipole moment.

Physical and Chemical Properties of the Hexachlorocyclohexanes

In pure state the isomers are well defined colorless crystals, practically insoluble in water and soluble in almost all organic solvents. Of the isomers, δ is the most soluble and β is the least soluble in organic solvents, which is explained by the fact that the solubility is inversely proportional to the number of peripheral chlorine atoms, the β -isomer with maximum number (6) of peripheral chlorine atoms being the least soluble. The melting points of the isomers given in the following table are in agreement with the literature values (Slade, *loc. cit.*). The M. p. of β -isomer (196° - 210°) reported by Daasch (*loc. cit.*) is very low and is probably in error. The melting point increases with the number of peripheral chlorine atoms, the β -isomer with 6 peripheral chlorine atoms has the highest melting point (309°).

TABLE II

Isomer.	Occurrence.	M. p.	Solubility in C ₆ H ₆ .	Obs. $\mu \times 10^{18}$.	Mortality coefficient $K \times 10^3$ (a)
	(b)	$^{\circ}(a)$	(c)	(a)	
α	70%	158°	11.3	1.7	67.2
β	5	809°	1.12	0.0	0.24
γ	10-12	112.8°	33.7	2.55	160.80
δ	10	188°	40.2	0.0	18.5
ϵ	3	219°(c)	14.8	—	—

(a) Present authors.

(b) Slade (*loc. cit.*)(c) Kauer *et al.* (*loc. cit.*)

The heat of vaporisation of the isomers indicates that β -isomer has the lowest heat of vaporisation and sublimes easily owing to its symmetrical structure, γ has higher and δ has the highest heat of vaporisation due to one and two polar chlorine atoms. The study of the infra-red spectra of the isomers (Daasch, *loc. cit.*) indicates that the β -isomer has the simplest spectra due to its symmetry. The α -isomer, which belongs to the flexible type, has a complex spectra.

The alkaline dehydrochlorination of the isomers yields a mixture of trichlorobenzenes. The action of alcoholic potash on the hexachlorocyclohexanes is quite distinctive to identify the isomers. The β -isomer is not at all affected by such treatment. α -Isomer is most readily dehydrochlorinated owing to its flexible nature. Next in the ease of hydrolysis comes the δ -isomer which is characterised by two polar chlorine atoms in *para* position, and which is understandable on the basis of the well known *para* linkage in benzene. The γ -isomer is less easily hydrolysed than the δ form owing to its single chlorine atom. The resistance to hydrolysis thus increases with the number of peripheral chlorine atoms. The ϵ -isomer is less readily hydrolysed than γ owing to the two chlorine atoms in the *ortho* position offering steric hindrance. S. J. Cristal (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 339) has suggested a *trans* mode of elimination of HCl as more plausible than the *cis* mode. On this basis δ -isomer, which has two *trans* HCl, should be more easily dehydrochlorinated than γ , which has only one *trans* HCl. The behaviour of α -form can be easily explained as due to its flexible structure, the hydrogen and chlorine atoms can take up the required *trans* positions.

Insecticidal Action of the Isomers

The toxicity of the four isomers α , β , γ and δ to mosquito larvae and rats has been investigated by Haller and co-workers (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1947, 39, 468) as percentage mortality in certain time. We have calculated the mortality coefficient K by applying the law of unimolecular reaction,

$$K = \frac{2.3}{t} \log \frac{100}{100 - x}$$

It has been found (Kulkarni, *Ind. J. Mal.*, 1949, 3, 1) that K is independent of time and concentration. The correlation between the mortality coefficient and the dipole moment reveals the fact that the dipole moments vary linearly with the logarithm of the mortality coefficient, and that the γ -isomer, which possesses outstanding insecticidal properties, has the highest dipole moment. As however, the ϵ -isomer, which is reported to be non-toxic, is likely to have a moment of $3.6D$, it appears that the insecticidal property requires a certain optimum electric moment as in the case of the dissociation constants of sulphur compounds.

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